

Studies in Oxidation-Reduction Potential. Part II. Thioglycollic and Thiolaetic Acids.

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In the preceding paper, the oxidation-reduction potential of cystine and cysteine has been investigated in a solution at mercury cathode after forming the reductants *in situ* by the cathodic reduction of cystine in an atmosphere of pure nitrogen. The potential was shown to follow the thermodynamic equation

$$E = 0.793 - \frac{RT}{F} p_H - \frac{RT}{F} \log \frac{[\text{cysteine}]}{\sqrt{[\text{cystine}]}}$$

It was considered interesting to investigate the oxidation-reduction potentials of other sulphhydryl compounds, *e.g.* thioglycollic acid and thiolaetic acid by the same method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Two c.c. of a solution of thioglycollic acid or thiolaetic acid exactly neutralised with caustic soda solution was oxidized by an exactly equivalent quantity of hydrogen peroxide and made up to 100 c.c. with buffer solution. This was then introduced within the electrolytic cell. The p_H value of the buffer solution was always determined electrometrically. Kahlbaum's thioglycollic acid was used.

Thiolaetic acid was prepared from bromopropionic acid by potassium hydrosulphide by the method of Loven (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1884, 29, 367). It was finally distilled at 100°/15 mm.

Measurements were made at a temperature of 30°. Experimental results above p_H 7 can be formulated by the thermodynamic equation

$$E = 0.798 - \frac{RT}{F} p_H - \frac{RT}{F} \log \frac{[\text{reductant}]}{\sqrt{[\text{oxidant}]}} \quad \dots (1)$$

and also for the same p_H , the variation of *E.M.F.* with variation of the ratio of concentrations could be expressed by the equation

$$E_1 - E_2 = \frac{RT}{F} \log \frac{[\text{reductant}]_1 \cdot \sqrt{[\text{oxidant}]_2}}{\sqrt{[\text{oxidant}]_1} \cdot [\text{reductant}]_2} \quad (2)$$

Table I gives the potential at different p_H values and different concentrations of the oxidant and reductant.

TABLE I.

p_H	Mol. conc. oxidant.	Mol. conc. reductant.	E_0	E_{00}	$E_1 - E_2$	
					Obs.	Calc. from (2)
I. Thioglycollic acid.						
9.30 (i)	0.055	0.11	-0.4390	0.0772	0.0205	0.0161
,, (ii)	0.079	0.071	-0.4125	0.0802		
8.55 (i)	0.046	0.13	-0.3916	0.0791	0.0232	0.0229
,, (ii)	0.017	0.19	-0.4146	0.0781		
7.00 (i)	0.079	0.065	-0.2716	0.0808	0.0619	0.0617
,, (ii)	0.0037	0.15	-0.3334	0.0805		
II. Thiolactic acid.						
9.35 (i)	0.050	0.032	-0.4103	0.0789	0.0653	0.0647
,, (ii)	0.0049	0.12	-0.4756	0.0803		
7.85 (i)	0.042	0.023	-0.3116	0.0795	0.0318	0.0318
,, (ii)	0.024	0.059	-0.3434	0.0800		

Discussion.

It is remarkable that the value of E_0 should be the same for thiolactic acid and thioglycollic acid as for cysteine. It is clear therefore that the reaction

has a value of free energy which is independent of the nature of the free radical to which the sulphur atom of the sulphhydryl group is attached.

It is interesting to note in this connection that the Raman spectra of all mercaptans and that of H_2S are identical, the shift being 2578 cm^{-1} . The same value of the Raman shift indicates that the force binding the hydrogen atom to the sulphur atom is always the same and independent of the way in which the other valency bonds of sulphur atom are saturated.